

PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD -N.C.S-. PART XV. ACTION OF COPPER ACETATE ON PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE

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The action of copper acetate on phenylthiocarbamide has been investigated. At ordinary temperatures a part of phenylthiocarbamide is oxidised to Hector's base and the cuprous acetate produced simultaneously combines with the rest of the thiocarbamide to form a complex. This is comparable with the action of other copper salts already studied. In boiling solutions, however, it is remarkable that desulphurisation to phenylcyanamide also takes place even in the presence of considerable concentrations of acetic acid.

In continuation of the earlier work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 25) the action of copper acetate on phenylthiocarbamide has been investigated with the object of studying the action of the copper salt of a weak acid.

In the case of cupric sulphate or chloride it is found that the primary reaction of these copper salts with phenylthiocarbamide, irrespective of the variations in temperature, dilution, or the p_H of the medium, so long as it continues to be acidic, is the oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide to Hector's base (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1176), the copper salts being simultaneously reduced to the cuprous state. The cuprous salts so formed combine with unoxidised thiocarbamide to form various complexes depending upon the temperature of the medium. Temperature thus controls the extent of the primary oxidative change but the nature of the change remains essentially the same at ordinary as well as at boiling temperature.

In the case of copper acetate we have found that all the factors, viz., p_H , dilution and temperature of the medium influence the change both in its qualitative and quantitative aspects, the desulphurisation of a thiourea in acid solution being noteworthy.

At ordinary temperatures phenylthiocarbamide reduces copper acetate and forms a white complex with the reduced salt, the part of the phenylthiocarbamide, which undergoes oxidation, giving Hector's base (*cf.* the action of $CuSO_4$ and $CuCl_2$). The reaction may be roughly represented by the following equations :

The results of these experiments are presented below in Table I.

At higher temperature (boiling solutions) both oxidation and desulphurisation of phenylthiocarbamide proceed simultaneously ; but if an excess of free acetic acid be present in the system, oxidation is favoured at the expense of desulphurisation (*vide* Table II).

The graph in Fig. 1, shown at the end of the paper, brings out in a characteristic way the effect of increasing acid concentration on the processes of oxidation and desulphurisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Set I (At the ordinary temperatures)

1.52 G. (1/100 mole) of phenylthiocarbamide were suspended in 150 c.c. of water at the ordinary temperature and 50 c.c. of saturated solution of normal copper acetate added. The mixture on being vigorously stirred developed a turbidity and phenylthiocarbamide passed into solution. It was left overnight to complete the reaction when a white amorphous precipitate

separated out. It was filtered. Hector's base was precipitated from the filtrate by neutralisation with ammonium hydroxide, dried and weighed. Unused copper remaining in the liquors was estimated iodometrically. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

At ordinary temperature.

1.52 G. (1/100 mole) of phenylthiocarbamide were used and a saturated solution of normal copper added in excess.

Expt. No.	Dilution.	Conc. of acetic acid.	Copper used as CuAc for complex formation.	Hector's base isolated.
1	200 c.c.	5N	0.3045 g.	0.33 g.
2	200	2N	0.3076	0.30
3	200	N	...	0.28
4	200	N/2	0.3108	0.24
5	200	Nil	0.3076	Traces
6	1000	Nil	...	Nil

(i) In experiments 1 to 5 the same complex is formed. The amount of Hector's base isolated decreases from expt. 1 to 5 probably because in weaker acid solutions it is not completely retained in solution and gets precipitated along with the complex due to the hydrolysis of its acetate.

(ii) In experiment 5 the complex appeared to have a slightly blackish tinge.

(iii) In experiment 6 black residue of copper sulphide was obtained instead of a complex and from the solution on concentration phenylurea was isolated.

TABLE II

In boiling solutions.

3.04 G. of phenylthiourea (1/50 mole) were used
Dilution = 250 c.c.

Expt. No.	Ratio of phenylthiocarbamide : CuAc.	Medium.	Copper present (as CuAc)	Copper used up.	% of Hector's base formed	% α-Phenyl-cyanamide formed.*
1	1:2	Alkaline				83.0
2	1:1	Pure aq.	1.2714 g.	1.2714 g.	0.0 g.	40.0
3	1:2	"	2.5428	1.2570	0.0	46.0
4	1:1	N-NH ₄ Ac	1.2714	1.2700	0.0	39.1
5	"	N/2HAc	"	1.2300	<10.0	57.0
6	"	N "	"	1.2500	10.0-15.0	55.0
7	"	2N "	"	1.2700	28.0	45.0
8	"	3N "	"	"	39.0	30.0
9	"	4N "	"	"	48.0	17.3
10	"	5N "	"	"	65.0	<15.0

* Percentages of Hector's base and phenylcyanamide are calculated on the theoretical yields from 3.04 g. of phenylthiocarbamide.

Set II (In boiling solutions).

3.04 G. (1/50 mole) of phenylthiocarbamide were dissolved in boiling water and an equivalent quantity of copper acetate in the form of a concentrated solution of known strength, also at boiling temperature, were mixed and the burner removed immediately. The quantity of water was so chosen that the total bulk of the mixture was always about 250 c.c. In experiments in which an acidic medium was used, glacial acetic acid was added in the requisite quantity before the addition of copper acetate, care being taken that the final volume of the mixture did not exceed 250 c.c. The mixture was vigorously stirred and allowed to cool to the room temperature when it was filtered. The filtrate was made up to a measured volume and from a portion of it Hector's base was precipitated with an excess of strong aqueous ammonia. It was filtered, dried and weighed. From this quantity the total amount of Hector's base formed could be calculated.

Phenylcyanamide was precipitated as the silver salt from a known volume of the liquor. The precipitated silver salt was carefully collected, washed, dried and weighed.

Phenylcyanamide was also estimated volumetrically and there was good agreement in the results. They are summarised in Table II.

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that the figures for Hector's base isolated and copper used up are both too

high to be explained strictly on the equations given above. Some other complex with a lower percentage of phenylthiocarbamide is evidently formed, e.g., $(Ph'NH'CS'NH_2)_2CuAc$ (cf. reactions with other cupric salts where also a mixture of two complexes is obtained at ordinary temperatures, *loc. cit.*). Clearly the concentration of the free acid does not interfere with the course of the reaction. Experiments 5 and 6 bring out the effect of dilution. Excepting the result of experiment No. 6, where the change in the type of the reaction is owing to the hydrolysis of copper acetate on excessive dilution, the general trend at ordinary temperature is comparable with that of copper sulphate or copper chloride.

In boiling hot solutions (Table II), on the other hand, desulphurisation of phenylthiocarbamide takes place simultaneously, although with an increase in the concentration of free acetic acid in the medium, the formation of Hector's base is naturally augmented at the expense of desulphurisation. This is in sharp contrast to what obtains with copper sulphate and chloride under analogous conditions. The following suggestions are tentatively put forward to explain this very different behaviour of the acetic acid salt :

(i) Oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide is brought about by the normal salt, desulphurisation by the hydroxide formed as a result of hydrolysis. Hydrolysis of copper acetate even in presence of considerable quantities of free acetic acid is probable in boiling solutions.

(ii) The formation of as much as 65% Hector's base (*vide* Table II) cannot be reconciled with the formation of a complex, and it appears that the complexes $(Ph'thi)_2CuAc$ and $(Ph'thi)CuAc$, if formed at all, in boiling solutions, decompose into cuprous acetate and free phenylthiocarbamide. The cuprous acetate, so formed or produced as a result of the primary oxidative change, is further reduced to metallic copper, and additional oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide takes place, the total change being represented by the following equations :

It has in fact been found that while cuprous chloride and cuprous sulphate complexes are quite stable in boiling solutions, cuprous acetate complex decomposes under similar conditions.

(iii) It has been suggested under (ii) that in boiling strongly acidic solutions copper acetate is reduced to metallic copper oxidising phenylthiocarbamide. It is surprising to find that although copper acetate can thus be reduced, it fails to augment desulphurisation. The explanation probably lies in the fact that desulphurisation of a thiocarbamide requires the removal of two hydrogen atoms through their mobility on to the sulphur atom (*vide* Part XIV) which in a strongly acidic solution of a weak acid such as acetic acid, or in dilute solutions of strong acids is hindered through a process of salt formation, thus :

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